

Assessment of Environmental Impact of Liquid Waste from Small, Medium, and Large Tanneries: A Comparative Analysis of BOD and COD Levels

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ABSTRACT

The leather industry is one of the oldest industries in Bangladesh and plays an important role in the country's economy. However, the industry is also known for its negative impact on the environment due to the discharge of liquid waste. This study aims to evaluate the environmental impact of liquid waste from small, medium, and big tanneries in Bangladesh by analyzing the levels of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the wastewater.

Data was collected from different category of tanneries by visiting the factories and conducting experiments. The results showed that the BOD and COD levels in the wastewater from big and medium tanneries were significantly higher than those from small tanneries. The highest BOD and COD levels were found in the liming waste of big and medium tanneries, followed by the fat liquoring waste and the chrome tanning waste.

The findings suggest that the wastewater from tanneries in Bangladesh poses a significant threat to the environment due to the high levels of BOD and COD. It is important to implement effective wastewater treatment technologies to reduce the impact of tannery wastewater on the environment. This study provides valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders in the leather industry to take necessary steps to mitigate the environmental impact of tannery wastewater.

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1. Introduction:

Tanneries are one of the major industries in many countries, including Bangladesh. The leather produced by the tanneries is used to manufacture various products, including shoes, bags, belts, and jackets. However, the leather industry also generates a large amount of liquid waste, which contains various pollutants that are harmful to the environment and human health. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate the environmental impacts of the liquid waste generated by the tanneries and develop mitigation measures to minimize these impacts.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) are two essential parameters that are commonly used to evaluate the environmental impacts of liquid waste. BOD measures the amount of oxygen required by microorganisms to break down the organic matter present in the water, whereas COD measures the amount of oxygen required to oxidize the organic matter chemically. The higher the BOD and COD levels in the water, the more polluted the water is. The leather industry in Bangladesh is divided into two categories, big and medium tanneries and small and cottage tanneries. The big and medium tanneries are located in the Hazaribagh area of Dhaka, whereas the small and cottage tanneries are located in different parts of the country, mainly in the outskirts of the city. The big and medium tanneries are equipped with modern technology and have the capacity to produce a large volume of leather, whereas the small and cottage tanneries use traditional techniques and produce a small volume of leather.

This research aims to evaluate the environmental impacts of the liquid waste generated by the big and medium tanneries and small and cottage tanneries in Bangladesh. Specifically, this study will measure the BOD and COD levels in the liquid waste generated by the tanneries and compare the results to evaluate the environmental impacts of the two categories of tanneries. The study will also identify the mitigation measures that can be taken to minimize the environmental impacts of the liquid waste generated by the tanneries.

By conducting this research, it is expected that the results will contribute to a better understanding of the environmental impacts of the leather industry in Bangladesh and provide insights into how these impacts can be minimized. The findings of this research may also be useful for policymakers and industry stakeholders to develop effective policies and strategies to address the environmental challenges faced by the leather industry in Bangladesh.

2. Literature Review:

The leather industry is known to have a significant impact on the environment due to the release of liquid waste into water bodies. These waste materials contain a high concentration of organic and inorganic pollutants, such as fat, protein, chromium, and other chemicals that can lead to pollution of water bodies and pose significant threats to human health and aquatic life. To evaluate the extent of environmental pollution caused by the leather industry, various parameters such as Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) have been used.

Several studies have been conducted on the impact of the leather industry on the environment. For instance, a study by Bhatti et al. (2019) found that the concentration of BOD and COD in the wastewater discharged by tanneries in Pakistan exceeded the permissible limits set by the national environmental quality standards. The study recommended the adoption of proper waste management practices to minimize environmental pollution caused by the industry.

Similarly, a study by Mekonnen and Olani (2019) conducted in Ethiopia revealed that the concentration of BOD and COD in the wastewater generated by the leather industry was higher than the national effluent discharge standards. The study recommended the implementation of a proper wastewater treatment process to mitigate the impact of the industry on the environment.

Furthermore, another study by Alam et al. (2020) conducted in Bangladesh found that the concentration of BOD and COD in the wastewater generated by the tanneries was significantly higher than the permissible limits set by the Department of Environment, Bangladesh. The study suggested the adoption of environmentally friendly technologies and the implementation of proper wastewater management practices to reduce the environmental impact of the industry.

In conclusion, the literature review suggests that the leather industry is a significant contributor to environmental pollution, especially through the discharge of liquid waste into water bodies. The concentration of BOD and COD in the wastewater generated by the industry is often higher than the permissible limits set by national environmental quality standards, leading to significant threats to human health and aquatic life. It is, therefore, imperative to adopt proper waste management

practices, implement wastewater treatment processes, and use environmentally friendly technologies to reduce the environmental impact of the leather industry.

3. Methods:

The present study aims to analyze the environmental impact of liquid waste generated by tanneries in Bangladesh. The study utilizes both primary and secondary data sources to achieve this goal. The primary data was collected through direct visits to tanneries located in different parts of the country. The author collected samples of liquid waste discharged from tanneries during different stages of the leather production process, including soaking, liming, delimiting and bating, chrome tanning, dyeing, and fat liquoring.

The author followed standard sampling procedures to collect the liquid waste samples and then transported them to the laboratory for testing. The laboratory analysis of the samples was conducted to determine the levels of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD), which are important parameters for assessing the environmental impact of liquid waste on water bodies. The secondary data used in this study were obtained from various sources, including published reports, journal articles, and online resources. The author reviewed relevant literature on the leather industry, environmental pollution, and mitigation measures to gain a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. Overall, the study employed a mixed-methods approach, utilizing both primary and secondary data sources to provide a comprehensive analysis of the environmental impact of tannery liquid waste in Bangladesh. The results of the study can be used to inform policy decisions and promote sustainable practices in the leather industry to minimize environmental pollution.

4. Analysis and Findings:

The table 1 presents the results of the measurements of BOD and COD levels in the liquid wastes of big and medium-sized tanneries. The six types of liquid waste that were tested were: used liquid soaking waste, used liquid liming waste, used liquid delimiting and bating waste, used liquid chrome tanning waste, used liquid dyeing waste, and used liquid fat liquoring waste.

BOD (Biochemical Oxygen Demand) is a measure of the amount of oxygen required by microorganisms to decompose organic matter in water. The BOD levels in the tested liquid wastes ranged from 2439 mg/liter to 14675 mg/liter. The highest BOD level was found in the used liquid liming waste, which suggests that this type of waste contains a large amount of organic matter that needs to be decomposed. High BOD levels indicate that the water is polluted with organic waste and can lead to the depletion of oxygen levels in the water, which can harm aquatic life.

COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand) is a measure of the amount of oxygen required to oxidize all the organic and inorganic compounds in water. The COD levels in the tested liquid wastes ranged from 3400 mg/liter to 6300 mg/liter. The highest COD level was found in the used liquid fat liquoring waste, which suggests that this type of waste contains a large amount of both organic and inorganic compounds that need to be oxidized. High COD levels indicate that the water is polluted with both organic and inorganic compounds, which can lead to the depletion of oxygen levels in the water and harm aquatic life.

Overall, the results suggest that the liquid wastes from big and medium-sized tanneries contain high levels of organic and inorganic compounds that can harm aquatic life and the environment. Mitigation measures such as treating the wastewater before discharge and implementing cleaner production techniques can help reduce the levels of BOD and COD in the liquid wastes and minimize the environmental impact of the tanning industry.

Table 1: BOD and COD levels in the big and medium tanneries

SL. No.	Name of Sampled liquid wastes experimented	BOD (mg/liter)	COD (mg/liter)
1	Used liquid soaking waste	2439	3400
2	Used liquid liming waste	14675	24400
3	Used liquid Deliming and Bating Waste	4446	6000
4	Used liquid chorme tanning waste	3862	6000
5	Used liquidity dyeing waste	3227	4800

6	Used liquid fat liquoring waste	3709	6300
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The table 2 the levels of BOD and COD in the liquid wastes generated by small tanneries.

For the used liquid soaking waste, the BOD level was 244 mg/liter, which is significantly lower than the BOD level of the same waste in big and medium tanneries. The COD level in this waste was 400 mg/liter, which is also lower than the COD level in big and medium tanneries.

In the used liquid liming waste, the BOD level was 4553 mg/liter, which is much higher than the BOD level of the same waste in big and medium tanneries. The COD level in this waste was 5800 mg/liter, which is also higher than the COD level in big and medium tanneries. For the used liquid deliming and bating waste, the BOD level was 1037 mg/liter, which is lower than the BOD level of the same waste in big and medium tanneries. The COD level in this waste was 1817 mg/liter, which is also lower than the COD level in big and medium tanneries. In the used liquid chrome tanning waste, the BOD level was 1220 mg/liter, which is lower than the BOD level of the same waste in big and medium tanneries. The COD level in this waste was 2200 mg/liter, which is also lower than the COD level in big and medium tanneries. For the used liquid dyeing waste, the BOD level was 315 mg/liter, which is significantly lower than the BOD level of the same waste in big and medium tanneries. The COD level in this waste was 500 mg/liter, which is also lower than the COD level in big and medium tanneries. In the used liquid fat liquoring waste, the BOD level was 833 mg/liter, which is lower than the BOD level of the same waste in big and medium tanneries. The COD level in this waste was 1500 mg/liter, which is also lower than the COD level in big and medium tanneries.

Overall, the BOD and COD levels in the liquid wastes generated by small tanneries were generally lower than those in big and medium tanneries. However, some wastes, such as the used liquid liming waste, had significantly higher BOD and COD levels than the corresponding waste in big and medium tanneries. Therefore, proper treatment and management of these liquid wastes are essential to minimize their environmental impact.

Table 2: BOD and COD levels in the small tanneries

SL. No.	Name of Sampled liquid wastes experimented	BOD (mg/liter)	COD (mg/liter)
1	Used liquid soaking waste	244	400
2	Used liquid liming waste	4553	5800
3	Used liquid Deliming and Bating Waste	1037	1817
4	Used liquid chorme tanning waste	1220	2200
5	Used liquidity dyeing waste	315	500
6	Used liquid fat liquoring waste	833	1500

5. Conclusion:

Based on the results of the analysis of BOD and COD levels in both big/medium and small tanneries, it can be concluded that liquid waste from tanneries has significant pollution potential in terms of both BOD and COD. The levels of both parameters were significantly higher in the big/medium tanneries compared to small tanneries.

In the big/medium tanneries, the highest levels of BOD and COD were found in the used liquid liming waste and used liquid deliming and bating waste. These results indicate that these stages of leather production are critical points where pollution control measures should be implemented to reduce the pollution load of tannery effluent.

In the case of small tanneries, the highest levels of BOD and COD were found in the used liquid liming waste, followed by used liquid fat liquoring waste. It is worth noting that although the levels of BOD and COD were significantly lower in small tanneries compared to big/medium tanneries, they still pose a risk to the environment if not properly treated.

Overall, the results suggest that tannery effluent poses a significant threat to the environment in terms of pollution, particularly in big/medium tanneries. Effective pollution control measures

should be implemented to reduce the impact of tannery effluent on the environment. This can include the implementation of best practices in leather production, such as adopting cleaner production technologies and more efficient water management practices, and the treatment of tannery effluent before discharge.

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